

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Optimal quadrature formula for the approximate calculation of a singular integral

Shadimetov Kh. M.

*V.I.Romanovskiy Institute of Mathematics, Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences, Tashkent;
Tashkent State Transport University, Uzbekistan
kholmatshadimetov@mail.ru*

Jabborov Kh. Kh.

*V.I.Romanovskiy Institute of Mathematics, Uzbekistan Academy of Sciences, Tashkent;
University of World Economy and Diplomacy, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
jabborovx@bk.ru*

Keywords: Hilbert space, singular integral, error functional, optimal quadrature formula, singular integral equations, Hilbert kernel.

Statement of the problem

We consider the following quadrature formula

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \varphi(x) \cot \frac{x-t}{2} dx \cong \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_{\beta} \varphi(x_{\beta}), \quad (1)$$

where C_{β} are coefficients, x_{β} are nodal points, and $x_{\beta} \in [0, 2\pi]$. The functions $\varphi(x)$ belong to the Hilbert space $L_2^{(3)}(0, 2\pi)$, which is defined as

$$L_2^{(3)}(0, 2\pi) = \{\varphi(x) : [0, 2\pi] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}, \varphi''(x) \text{ is absolutely continuous, } \varphi'''(x) \in L_2(0, 2\pi)\}.$$

In this $L_2^{(3)}(0, 2\pi)$ space, the inner product of functions φ and ψ is defined as follows

$$\langle \varphi, \psi \rangle = \int_0^{2\pi} \varphi'''(x) \psi'''(x) dx, \quad (2)$$

and the norm of the function φ in this space is calculated using the inner product (??) as follows

$$\|\varphi\| = \sqrt{\int_0^{2\pi} (\varphi'''(x))^2 dx}. \quad (3)$$

The difference between the integral and the quadrature sum in the considered quadrature formula (1)

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^{2\pi} \varphi(x) \cot \frac{x-t}{2} dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \varphi(x_\beta) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (\varepsilon_{[0,2\pi]}(x) \cot \frac{x-t}{2} - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \delta(x-x_\beta)) \varphi(x) dx = \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \ell(x) \varphi(x) dx = (\ell, \varphi) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

is called the *error* of the quadrature formula.

For the derived expression (4), the following *error functional* corresponding to the conjugate space $L_2^{(3)*}(0, 2\pi)$ is obtained

$$\ell(x) = \varepsilon_{[0,2\pi]}(x) \cot \frac{x-t}{2} - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \delta(x-x_\beta), \quad (5)$$

where $\varepsilon_{[0,2\pi]}(x)$ is the characteristic function of the interval $[0, 2\pi]$, and $\delta(x)$ is Dirac's delta-function.

According to the definition of the norm of a linear continuous functional, the following is known:

$$\|\ell\|_{L_2^{(3)*}} = \sup_{\|\varphi\| \neq 0} \frac{|(\ell, \varphi)|}{\|\varphi\|}.$$

From this equality, the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality follows

$$|(\ell, \varphi)| \leq \|\ell\|_{L_2^{(3)*}} \|\varphi\|_{L_2^{(3)}}. \quad (6)$$

According to the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, the following conditions hold for the norm (3) of the function $\varphi(x)$

$$(\ell, x^\alpha) = 0, \quad \alpha = 0, 1, 2. \quad (7)$$

According to the conditions (7), the quadrature formula (1) is exact for the function $d_2x^2 + d_1x + d_0$. These conditions ensure that the error functional is bounded.

Thus, the upper bound of the error (4) of the quadrature formula (1) is estimated using the norm of the error functional $\ell(x)$. From this, the following problem arises.

Problem 1. Find the form of the norm of the error functional $\ell(x)$ belonging to the conjugate space $L_2^{(3)*}(0, 2\pi)$.

In this work, we solve the Sard problem. For this, we construct a quadrature formula at nodal points x_β where $x_\beta = h\beta$ ($h = \frac{2\pi}{N}$, $N \in \mathbb{N}$) are equidistantly distributed points.

The coefficients C_β that minimize the norm of the error functional $\ell(x)$, that is

$$\inf_{C_\beta} \|\ell\|_{L_2^{(3)*}(0,2\pi)} \quad (8)$$

are called *optimal coefficients* and are denoted by \mathring{C}_β . The quadrature formula constructed using these optimal coefficients is called an *optimal quadrature formula*. Therefore, to construct an optimal quadrature formula in the sense of Sard in the space $L_2^{(3)}(0, 2\pi)$, it is necessary to solve the following problem.

Problem 2. Find the optimal coefficients \mathring{C}_β that achieve the value in (8).

Finding the extremal function and expressing the norm of the error functional

To solve problem (1), that is, to find the form of the norm of the error functional (5), we use the concept of an extremal function.

The function $\psi_\ell(x)$ is called an *extremal function* corresponding to the error functional $\ell(x)$ if the following equality holds [1]

$$(\ell, \psi_\ell) = \|\ell\|_{L_2^{(3)*}} \cdot \|\psi_\ell\|_{L_2^{(3)}}. \quad (9)$$

The concept of an extremal function was first introduced by S.L. Sobolev and is defined as follows

$$\psi_\ell = -\ell(x) * G_3(x) + P_2(x),$$

where $G_3(x) = \frac{|x|^5}{2 \cdot 5!}$, and $P_2(x)$ is a second-degree polynomial.

We note that $*$ is the convolution and the convolution of two functions

$$\varphi(x) * \psi(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \varphi(x-y)\psi(y)dy = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \varphi(y)\psi(x-y)dy$$

is defined by the formula.

Since the space $L_2^3(0, 2\pi)$ we are considering is a Hilbert space, we present the Riesz theorem on the general form of a linear continuous functional.

(Riesz theorem) Let H be a Hilbert space. Then for each linear continuous functional $\ell \in H^*$, there exists a unique function ψ_ℓ in the space H itself, called the Riesz element, which satisfies the condition $(\ell, \varphi) = \langle \psi_\ell, \varphi \rangle$ corresponding to this functional, and the following equality holds for this function

$$\|\ell\|_{H^*} = \|\psi_\ell\|_H$$

and conversely.

For any $\psi_\ell \in H$, there exists a unique functional $\ell \in H^*$ that satisfies the conditions $(\ell, \varphi) = \langle \psi_\ell, \varphi \rangle$ and $\|\ell\|_{H^*} = \|\psi_\ell\|_H$.

According to the theorem, the extremal function $\psi_\ell(x)$ is a Riesz element and

$$(\ell, \psi_\ell) = \|\ell\|^2 = \|\psi_\ell\|^2.$$

Based on the theorem, we calculate the square of the norm of the error functional

$$\begin{aligned} \|\ell\|^2 = & - \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{|x-y|^5}{2 \cdot 5!} \cot \frac{x-t}{2} \cot \frac{y-t}{2} dx dy + \\ & + 2 \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{|x-h\beta|^5}{2 \cdot 5!} \cot \frac{x-t}{2} dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N \sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\beta C_\gamma \frac{|h\beta-h\gamma|^5}{2 \cdot 5!} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Thus, the square of the norm of the error functional $\ell(x)$ has been determined, and problem 1 has been solved.

Finding the conditional minimum of the error functional

Now we will tackle the second problem. The square of the norm of the error functional obtained in (10) is a multi-variable function with respect to the coefficients C_β . According to the rule for finding the conditional extremum of a multi-variable function, we will determine its local minimum in conjunction with the conditions (7). To achieve this, we construct the Lagrange function:

$$\Phi(C_\beta, d_2, d_1, d_0) = \|\ell\|^2 + 2 \sum_{\alpha=0}^2 d_\alpha(\ell, x^\alpha), \quad \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N.$$

According to (7), the following holds true here

$$(\ell, x^\alpha) = \int_0^{2\pi} x^\alpha \cot \frac{x-t}{2} dx - \sum_{\beta=0}^N C_\beta (h\beta)^\alpha = 0, \quad \alpha = 0, 1, 2.$$

By setting the partial derivatives of the resulting function Φ with respect to the coefficients C_β and the unknowns d_2, d_1, d_0 to zero, we obtain the following system of linear equations

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\gamma \frac{|h\beta-h\gamma|^5}{2 \cdot 5!} + d_2(h\beta)^2 + d_1(h\beta) + d_0 = f_3(h\beta), \quad \beta = 0, 1, \dots, N, \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\gamma (h\gamma)^2 = g_2, \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\gamma (h\gamma) = g_1, \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{\gamma=0}^N C_\gamma = g_0, \quad (14)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
f_3(h\beta) &= \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{|x - h\beta|^5}{2 \cdot 5!} \cot \frac{x - t}{2} dx = \\
&= \frac{1}{5!} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k+5)(2k)!} \left((2\pi - t)^{2k+5} - 2(h\beta - t)^{2k+5} - t^{2k+5} \right) + \right. \\
&\quad + 5(t - h\beta) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k+4)(2k)!} \left((2\pi - t)^{2k+4} - 2(h\beta - t)^{2k+4} + t^{2k+4} \right) + \\
&\quad + 10(t - h\beta)^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k+3)(2k)!} \left((2\pi - t)^{2k+3} - 2(h\beta - t)^{2k+3} - t^{2k+3} \right) + \\
&\quad + 10(t - h\beta)^3 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k+2)(2k)!} \left((2\pi - t)^{2k+2} - 2(h\beta - t)^{2k+2} + t^{2k+2} \right) + \\
&\quad \left. + 5(t - h\beta)^4 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k+1)(2k)!} \left((2\pi - t)^{2k+1} - 2(h\beta - t)^{2k+1} - t^{2k+1} \right) + \right. \\
&\quad \left. + 2(t - h\beta)^5 \ln \left| \frac{\sin \frac{t}{2}}{\sin \frac{h\beta - t}{2}} \right| \right], \\
g_2 &= 2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k+2)(2k)!} \left((2\pi - t)^{2k+2} - t^{2k+2} \right) + \\
&\quad + 4t \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k+1)(2k)!} \left((2\pi - t)^{2k+1} + t^{2k+1} \right), \\
g_1 &= 2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{B_{2k}}{(2k+1)(2k)!} \left((2\pi - t)^{2k+1} + t^{2k+1} \right), \\
g_0 &= \int_0^{2\pi} \cot \frac{x - t}{2} dx = 0,
\end{aligned}$$

here, B_{2k} are the Bernoulli numbers, and the following formula was used [3]

$$\int x^p \cot x dx = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (-1)^k \frac{2^{2k} B_{2k}}{(2k+p)(2k)!} x^{2k+p}, \quad [p \geq 1, |x| < \pi].$$

The system (11)-(14) consists of $(N+4)$ unknowns and $(N+4)$ linear equations with respect to $C_\gamma, \gamma = 0, 1, \dots, N, d_0, d_1, d_2$. To solve this system, we will employ the functional method proposed by Sobolev. For this method, it is crucial to use a discrete analogue of the differential operator d^6/dx^6 .

The discrete analog of the differential operator d^6/dx^6 satisfying the equality $D_3(h\beta) * G_3(h\beta) = \delta(h\beta)$ has the following form [2]

$$D_3(h\beta) = \frac{5!}{h^6} \begin{cases} \sum_{t=1}^2 K_t \cdot q_t^{|\beta|-1}, & |\beta| \geq 2, \\ 1 + \sum_{t=1}^2 K_t, & |\beta| = 1, \\ -2^5 + \sum_{t=1}^2 \frac{K_t}{q_t}, & \beta = 0, \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where $\delta(h\beta)$ is a discrete delta function, $K_1 = \frac{(1-q_1)^7}{E_5(q_1)}$, $K_2 = \frac{(1-q_2)^7}{E_5(q_2)}$, $E_5(x)$ is a fifth-degree Euler-Frobenius polynomial, and q_1 and q_2 are roots of the Euler-Frobenius polynomial $E_4(q)$ satisfying the inequality $|q_t| < 1$, ($t = 1, 2$).

The optimal coefficients of the quadrature formula (1), with nodes equidistantly spaced in the space $L_2^{(3)}(0, 2\pi)$, have the following form

$$\begin{aligned} C_0 = & \frac{5!}{h^5} \left[\frac{g_1 h^4}{48} + \frac{g_2 h^3}{24} + a_2^- h^2 - a_1^- h - 31 \cdot f_3(0) + f_3(1) + \sum_{n=1}^2 \frac{K_n F_n}{q_n} + \right. \\ & + \sum_{n=1}^2 \frac{K_n}{q_n} \left(\frac{D_{n4} g_1 h^4}{48} + \frac{D_{n3} g_2 h^3}{24} + D_{n2} a_2^- h^2 - D_{n1} a_1^- h + D_{n0} f_3(0) \right) + \\ & + \sum_{n=1}^2 K_n q_n^{N-1} \left(-\frac{D_{n4} g_1 h^4}{48} + D_{n3} h^3 \left(\frac{g_2}{24} - \frac{g_1 h N}{12} \right) + \right. \\ & \left. + D_{n2} h^2 \left(\frac{g_2 h N}{8} - \frac{g_1 h^2 N^2}{8} + a_2^+ \right) + D_{n1} h \left(\frac{g_2 h^2 N^2}{8} - \frac{g_1 h^3 N^3}{12} + 2a_2^+ h N + a_1^+ \right) + D_{n0} f_3(N) \right] ; \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_\beta = & \frac{5!}{h^5} \left[\sum_{n=1}^2 K_n q_n^{\beta-1} \left(\frac{D_{n4} g_1 h^4}{48} + \frac{D_{n3} g_2 h^3}{24} + D_{n2} a_2^- h^2 - D_{n1} a_1^- h + D_{n0} f_3(0) \right) + \right. \\ & + \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \sum_{n=1}^2 K_n q_n^{|\beta-\gamma|-1} f_3(\gamma) + f_3(\beta-1) - 32f_3(\beta) + f_3(\beta+1) + \\ & + \sum_{n=1}^2 K_n q_n^{N-\beta-1} \left(-\frac{D_{n4} g_1 h^4}{48} + \right. \\ & \left. + D_{n3} h^3 \left(\frac{g_2}{24} - \frac{g_1 h N}{12} \right) + D_{n2} h^2 \left(\frac{g_2 h N}{8} - \frac{g_1 h^2 N^2}{8} + a_2^+ \right) + \right. \\ & \left. + D_{n1} h \left(\frac{g_2 h^2 N^2}{8} - \frac{g_1 h^3 N^3}{12} + 2a_2^+ h N + a_1^+ \right) + D_{n0} f_3(N) \right] , \quad \beta = 1, 2, \dots, N-1; \end{aligned}$$

$$C_N = \frac{5!}{h^5} \left[-\frac{g_1 h^4}{48} + \frac{g_2 h^3}{24} - \frac{g_1 h^4 N}{12} + \frac{g_2 h^3 N}{8} - \frac{g_1 h^4 N^2}{8} + \frac{g_2 h^3 N^2}{8} - \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{g_1 h^4 N^3}{12} + 2a_2^+ h^2 N + a_2^+ h^2 + a_1 h - 31 \cdot f_3(N) + f_3(N-1) + \\
& + \sum_{n=1}^2 K_n q_n^{N-1} \left(\frac{D_{n4} g_1 h^4}{48} + \frac{D_{n3} g_2 h^3}{24} + D_{n2} a_2^- h^2 - D_{n1} a_1^- h + D_{n0} f_3(0) \right) + \\
& + \sum_{n=1}^2 \sum_{\gamma=0}^N K_n q_n^{N-\gamma-1} f_3(\gamma) + \sum_{n=1}^2 \frac{K_n}{q_n} \left(-\frac{D_{n4} g_1 h^4}{48} + D_{n3} h^3 \left(\frac{g_2}{24} - \frac{g_1 h N}{12} \right) + \right. \\
& \quad \left. + D_{n2} h^2 \left(\frac{g_2 h N}{8} - \frac{g_1 h^2 N^2}{8} + a_2^+ \right) + \right. \\
& \quad \left. + D_{n1} h \left(\frac{g_2 h^2 N^2}{8} - \frac{g_1 h^3 N^3}{12} + 2a_2^+ h N + a_1^+ \right) + D_{n0} f_3(N) \right) \Bigg];
\end{aligned}$$

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SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
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garniturada raqamli bosma usulida bosildi.
Shartli bosma tabog'i: 28,5. Adadi: 100.

"Noble Print" MChJ bosmaxonasida chop etildi.
100194, Toshkent shahri, Yunusobod-11, 62-uy.